

Management

RECRUITMENT AND SELECTION STRATEGIES OF PUBLIC SECTOR UNDERTAKINGS

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of recruitment and selection strategies of public sector undertaking .In the Indian context, Public sector or the PSEs primarily constitute the corporate bodies where 51% or more equity is held by the government, created under the special acts of legislature, or registered under the companies Act 1956.Primary data on various aspects of recruitment and selection were collected from the employees of different undertakings with the help of well framed questionnaire that was duly filled by the HRM officials and employees. This study highlight the emerging trends in the recruitment and selection strategies of public sector undertaking and the major obstacles that are being faced by the companies.

Keywords: Recruitment and Selection; Sources of Recruitment; Selection Procedures.

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1. Introduction

In the modern industrial setup, Human Resource Management has become one of the most important functions of Management because it is concerned with human factor in the organizational performances, which by all accounts is the most important factor in all sorts' activities in business. For a long time it has been the practice to assign specific duties to functionary regarding recruitment, selection, training, wage determination and so on and so forth. As the new millennium unfolds itself, in today's complex and dynamic environment the challenges are significant in number and magnitude for the organizational managers. For effectively dealing with these challenges they have to possess the required knowledge and skills to diagnose what goes on in the environment, develop strategies for meeting new conditions, implementing such measures, which will sustain organizational health and validity.

1.1. Recruitment

The process of identification of different sources of personnel is known as recruitment. It is a positive process of searching qualified persons and stimulates them to apply for jobs in the establishment. It is an important task for the human resource managers as it helps in deciding the right candidate for a particular job.

According to Dale Yoder, “Recruitment is a process to discover the sources of manpower to meet the requirements of the staffing schedule and employee effective measures for attracting that manpower in adequate number to facilities effective selection of an efficient working force”.

1.2. Methods of Recruitment

- 1) Direct Methods
- 2) Indirect Methods

DIRECT METHODS includes scouting (campus interviews), employee contacts, manned exhibits and waiting lists. In INDIRECT METHODS vacancies are notified in newspapers, journals, radio and television media to recruit employees.

1.3. Sources of Recruitment

- 1) Internal Sources
- 2) External Sources

INTERNAL SOURCES includes,
Transfers:-

- 1) production transfer (department to department)
- 2) replacement transfer (another department)
- 3) rotation transfer (one job to another job to make them versatile)
- 4) remedial transfer (employee feels discomfort)

Promotions (based on seniority and competence, Demotions (reverse of promotion) etc.

EXTERNAL SOURCES includes

- 1) Notice at factory gate(put a notice at the factory gate by the organization)
- 2) Unsolicited applications (submit application by job seekers)
- 3) Casual callers(appoint for short period)
- 4) Advertisement (given in newspapers or trade or professional journals)
- 5) Employment Exchange (for skilled, unskilled or semi-skilled persons)
- 6) Colleges, Institutions and Universities (fresh young graduates of different discipline)
- 7) Labour contractors (for unskilled labors)
- 8) Private agencies
- 9) Trade unions
- 10) Leasing

1.4.Selection

It is the process of choosing the most suitable persons from all the applicants. Selection process starts immediately after recruitment. Selection involves picking a group of workers from a local group of workers who has applied for job. According to Dale Yoder, "Selection is the process in which candidates for employment are divided into two classes those who are to be offered employment and those who are not".

1.5.Steps in Selection Process

1) Receipt and Scrutiny of Application

If there are vacancies it will be notified in newspaper, notice board etc. Numbers of applicants are received candidates. After the prescribed date personnel department makes a detailed scrutiny of application.

2) Preliminary Interviews

It is the basic interview. It is normally conducted by the assistant or secretary of personnel department. Appearance and personality of the candidates are also examined.

3) Blank Application Form

A blank application form is given to candidates. They are required to fill up the application form in their own handwriting. These are printed applications used to collect the individual bio-data of the candidates

4) Tests

After preliminary interview, the candidates are asked to appear for selection tests. It is mainly to examine the suitability of the candidate for a job. The management should like to know the capabilities and the knowledge, the pattern of interest, skill and aptitude of an individual in terms of job specification. For this purpose different types of tests are used. The important types of tests are intelligence test, trade test, aptitude test, interest test and personality test.

5) Interview

Interview is a powerful exchange of ideas, the answering of questions, and communicating between two or more persons. The interview enables the candidate to get information about the nature of job, compensation package, working conditions etc.

6) Checking References

In the blank application form there is a column for giving references. The candidates are required to write the names of one or two important respected persons in his/her locality. So the employer can enquire about the candidate from these referees.

7) Approval of the Supervisor

The name and details of the candidate selected is sent to the supervisor for approval.

8) Medical Examination

The qualified candidate is required to go for medical examination. He/she will be examined by a doctor to check whether he/she is suffering from any disease which will render him/her physically unfit for the job.

9) Final Selection

After completing all the above formalities the successful candidates are given appointment order.

10) Placement

When the candidate is selected and appointed, he/she is posted to a particular position for which he/she is selected. Placement means the determination of the job to which an accepted candidate is to be assigned to that job.

11) Induction or Orientation

It is the process of inducting an employee into the social set up of his/her work. It is a welcoming process through which he/she feels at home, and a feeling is generated in him/her that is his/her own job and his/her own organizations.

2. Statement of the Problem

Fast changes are taking place in the business environment. Modern world is dynamic in nature due to scientific and technological development. In this competitive world, the companies have to success they can appoint right person s at right place at right time. An organization must have the ability to observe the changes at a fast rate than in the past, not simply to prove its competency alone but to justify ours existence in the dynamic business world. All organizations whether large or small, must ensure themselves that they have the competent people capable of accepting this challenges.

3. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study is to overview the recruitment and selection strategies of public sector undertakings and to determine which recruitment and selection practices are more effective.

4. Data Collection

Primary data on various aspects of recruitment and selection were collected from the employees of different undertakings with the help of well framed questionnaire that was duly filled by the HRM officials and employees. The updated information in this area is gathered resources available at Bharathiar University and Published Net Resources. Data also collected from journal of Personnel Management, Southern Economists, and Business Industrial Journals.

5. Methodology

The validity of any research depends on the systematic method of collecting the data and analysis them as perfectly as to the extent of its best results. In this study primary data and secondary data were extensively used.

6. Tools Used for Analysis

- 1) Percentage Analysis
- 2) Factor Analysis

7. Review of Literature

Shelia M.Rioux, and **Paul Bernathai** stated that, better recruitment and selection strategies results in improved organizational outcomes. The more effectively organizations recruit and select candidates, the more likely they are to hire and retain satisfied employees.

According to Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, “the turning point in the process of growing up is when you the core strength within you that survives all hurt”.

According to Leon Megginson, the human resource can be thought of as “the knowledge, skills, creative abilities, talents and aptitude of an organizations workforce, as well as value, attitudes and beliefs of the individuals involved”

8. Limitations of the Study

- 1) Most of the primary data elicited from the employees are based on recall method and are, therefore subject to normal recall error
- 2) It was not quite possible to contact more than the selected number of respondents
- 3) Non availability of accurate data
- 4) Behavioral pattern of employees and management.

9. Summary of Findings and Conclusion

In the Indian economy, both the public and private sector has an important role as well as placing. Both operate in almost all sectors of the economy, although their relative positions differ widely in different sectors. Public sector undertakings have grown rapidly in many fields of economic activity involving massive investments. They have contributed a lot of progress to the Indian economy. The study was conducted mainly in public sector undertakings.

The companies are appointing workers on the basis of different norms. But the survey shows all that in all the firms there is recruitment policy. The data reveals that the recruitment is doing mainly on the basis of qualification and experience .It was supported by most of the workers are satisfied with the recruitment of the public sector undertakings.

From the study conclude that the recruitment and selection strategies of public sector undertakings are based on the direct method are good. From the frequency and cross tabulation we infer that direct method is more effective than indirect method.

References

- [1] Recruitment and Selection Practices
- [2] By Shelia M Rioux.Ph.D., and Paul AND Bernthal, Ph D.
- [3] Hrd Times---The Multifaceted Magazine, Vol.8.Nov-2006, p 27.
- [4] Recruiting and Job Search p 235 HRM Fifth edition
- [5] Cynthia D .Fisher .Ph. D. & James. B. ,Shaw, Ph D-Bond University
- [6] HRM & Industrial Relations
- [7] (Text, Cases & Games) p-135-Dr. Subha Rao S.K. Institute of Management
- [8] Essentials of Human Resource Management and industrial relations P.Subha Rao.